

Chang et al 2022. Genetic correlations between life history traits

```
#rm(list = ls())  
library(here)
```

```
## Warning: package 'here' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## here() starts at C:/Users/katel/Dropbox/Chang et al 2022
```

```
library(rotl)
```

```
## Warning: package 'rotl' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(ape)  
library(metafor)
```

```
## Warning: package 'metafor' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Loading required package: Matrix
```

```
## Warning: package 'Matrix' was built under R version 4.2.2
```

```
## Loading required package: metadat
```

```
## Warning: package 'metadat' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Loading required package: numDeriv
```

```
##
```

```
## Loading the 'metafor' package (version 4.0-0). For an  
## introduction to the package please type: help(metafor)
```

```
library(dplyr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'dplyr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
##
```

```
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:ape':
```

```
##
```

```
## where
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':  
##  
##   filter, lag
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':  
##  
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union
```

```
library(tidyr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'tidyr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'tidyr'
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:Matrix':  
##  
##   expand, pack, unpack
```

```
library(orchard)
```

```
##  
## Loading the 'orchard' package (version 2.0). For an  
## introduction and vignette to the package please see: https://danielnoble.github.io/orchard/
```

```
# install.packages("devtools")  
# library(devtools)  
# install_github("danielnoble/metaAidR")  
library(metaAidR)
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'metaAidR'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:metafor':  
##  
##   vcalc
```

```
library(car)
```

```
## Warning: package 'car' was built under R version 4.2.2
```

```
## Loading required package: carData
```

```
## Warning: package 'carData' was built under R version 4.2.2
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'car'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:dplyr':  
##  
##   recode
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:metafor':  
##  
##   vif
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
## Warning: package 'ggplot2' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(ggpubr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'ggpubr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'ggpubr'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:ape':  
##  
##   rotate
```

```
here()
```

```
## [1] "C:/Users/katel/Dropbox/Chang et al 2022"
```

1. input data

```
data_processed_full <- read.csv("SData_3_data_processed_full_20221205.csv")  
nlevels(unique(as.factor(data_processed_full$key))) #142 papers
```

```
## [1] 142
```

```
sum(is.na(data_processed_full$zr_sign)) #139
```

```
## [1] 139
```

```
#remove na in zr_sign  
data_processed_full <- data_processed_full[!is.na(data_processed_full$zr_sign),]  
nlevels(unique(as.factor(data_processed_full$key)))#140
```

```
## [1] 140
```

```

#set as factors
cols <- c("ID", "key", "species", "lab_field", "sex", "stage", "selection", "narrow_broad",
          "measure_1", "measure_2", "trait_1", "trait_2", "trait_rename_1", "trait_rename_2", "Group", "Design")
data_processed_full[cols] <- lapply(data_processed_full[cols], as.factor)
sum(is.na(data_processed_full$zr_sign))

```

```
## [1] 0
```

```
nrow(data_processed_full)
```

```
## [1] 1886
```

```

#add trait pair
data_processed_full$pair <- paste0(data_processed_full$trait_rename_1, "-", data_processed_full$trait_rename_2)

data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "fertility-survival"] <- "survival-fertility"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "maturation-survival"] <- "survival-maturation"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "growth-survival"] <- "survival-growth"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "size-survival"] <- "survival-size"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "maturation-growth"] <- "growth-maturation"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "fertility-growth"] <- "growth-fertility"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "size-growth"] <- "growth-size"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "fertility-maturation"] <- "maturation-fertility"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "size-maturation"] <- "maturation-size"
data_processed_full$pair[data_processed_full$pair == "size-fertility"] <- "fertility-size"

summary(as.factor(data_processed_full$pair))

```

```

##  fertility-fertility      fertility-size      growth-fertility
##                199                175                17
##    growth-growth      growth-maturation      growth-size
##                11                41                84
##  maturation-fertility  maturation-maturation      maturation-size
##                176                104                320
##        size-size      survival-fertility      survival-growth
##                122                282                30
##  survival-maturation      survival-size      survival-survival
##                122                109                94

```

1a. Optional: Load model results into environment

```

# some of these models take a long time to run so we saved all the outputs here
# you can load these to reproduce results as desired

# survival pair data
load("meta_survival.RData")
load("meta_survival_pair.RData")
load("meta_survival_lab.RData")
load("meta_survival_sex.RData")
load("meta_survival_stage.RData")

```

```

load("meta_survival_narrow.RData")
load("meta_survival_design.RData")

# non-survival pair data
load("meta_other.RData")
load("meta_other_pair.RData")
load("meta_other_lab.RData")
load("meta_other_sex.RData")
load("meta_other_stage.RData")
load("meta_other_narrow.RData")
load("meta_other_design.RData")

# pub bias data
load("meta_survival_se.RData")
load("meta_other_se.RData")
load("meta_survival_year.RData")
load("meta_other_year.RData")

```

2. build phylogeny which will be used as random effect for further models

```

# Here, we create and save taxonomic data. This file can be loaded to reproduce results as
# in the future as it's possible taxonomic groupings might be updated (and be different than the tree w

species <- sort(unique(data_processed_full$species))
species <- as.character(species)
# taxa <- tnrs_match_names(names = species, context = "Animals")
#
# # Saving the taxonomic data created on the 1st December 2023 to speed the
# # process in the future and allow full reproducibility
# save(taxa, file = "taxa_Open_Tree_of_Life.RData")

# Loading the taxonomic data
load("taxa_Open_Tree_of_Life.RData") #taxa

# #to check the species with more than one match
# taxa[taxa$number_matches > 1,]
# #they are all correct. search_string matches unique_name
#
# taxon_map <- structure(taxa$search_string, names = taxa$unique_name)
# tree <- tol_induced_subtree(ott_ids = taxa[["ott_id"]], label_format = "name")
# plot(tree, cex=.5, label.offset =.1, no.margin = TRUE)
#
# # We need to check for the existence of polytomies
# is.binary(tree)
#
# # to take care of these polytomies, we are going to use a
# # randomization approach
# set.seed(111) #making it reproducible
# tree <- multi2di(tree,random=TRUE)
# is.binary(tree)
#

```

```

# tree$tip.label[1:4]
# otl_tips <- strip_ott_ids(tree$tip.label, remove_underscores = TRUE)
# tree$tip.label <- taxon_map[ otl_tips ]
# tree$node.label <- NULL
#
# # check if inconsistency
# setdiff(as.character(tolower(species)), as.character(tree$tip.label))
# setdiff(as.character(tree$tip.label), as.character(tolower(species)))
#
# # Save for future analyses to speed up and allow full reproducibility
# save(tree, file = "tree.Rdata") #tree

# We can now load the saved tree
load("tree.Rdata") #tree

# distance matrix
tree_grafen <- compute.brlen(tree, method="Grafen", power=1) # Make ultrametric using Grafen's method
is.ultrametric(tree_grafen) #TRUE

```

```
## [1] TRUE
```

```

# tree_matrix <- vcv(tree_grafen, cor=TRUE)
#
# # Finally, save matrix for future analyses to speed up and allow full reproducibility
# save(tree_matrix, file = "tree_matrix.Rdata")

# we can now load the saved matrix
load("tree_matrix.Rdata") #tree_matrix

# pdf("figure_output/tree.pdf",width=8,height=12)
plot(tree_grafen , cex=0.55)

```



```
# dev.off()
```

```
data_processed_full$animal <- tolower(data_processed_full$species)
data_processed_full$animal <- as.factor(data_processed_full$animal)
```

3. calculate vZ_r (sampling variance in effect size Z_r) and add observation level

```
data_processed_full$raw_vi <- 1/(data_processed_full$n-3)
data_processed_full$obs <- 1:nrow(data_processed_full)
data <- data_processed_full
```

```
survival_pair_data <- data[(data$trait_rename_1 == "survival" | data$trait_rename_2 == "survival") & data$obs == 1]
other_pair_data <- data[(!(data$trait_rename_1 == "survival" | data$trait_rename_2 == "survival")) & data$obs == 1]
```

4. Survival pairs

4.1 intercept only model

Absolute heterogeneity (Q) is reported in the summary of the model (and reported in Table 3)

```
meta_survival <- metafor::rma.mv(zr_sign, raw_vi, random= list(~ 1|species, ~ 1|animal, ~ 1|key, ~ 1|Group),
  R= list(animal = tree_matrix),
  data = survival_pair_data, method= "REML")
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(zr_sign, raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -469.7961  939.5921  951.5921  977.3637  951.7491
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0654 0.2557   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0001   37    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0277 0.1664   58    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0316 0.1779  161    no  Group   no
## sigma^2.5 0.2345 0.4843  543    no    obs    no
##
## Test for Heterogeneity:
## Q(df = 542) = 23815.5004, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
## estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## 0.1890 0.0641 2.9470 0.0032 0.0633 0.3148 **
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
predict(meta_survival)
```

```
##
##      pred      se  ci.lb  ci.ub  pi.lb  pi.ub
## 0.1890 0.0641 0.0633 0.3148 -0.9924 1.3704
```

```
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival), file = "model output/meta_survival.csv")
#save(meta_survival, file = "model/meta_survival.RData")
```

Estimates of relative heterogeneities due to different random effects (reported in Table 3)

```
I2_CI <- I2(meta_survival, survival_pair_data$raw_vi , ME = FALSE, sims = 10000, phylo = "animal", obs =
```

```
## Warning in class(model) != "MCMCglmm" && class(model) != "rma.mv": 'length(x) =
## 2 > 1' in coercion to 'logical(1)'
```

```
## Warning in class(model) != "MCMCglmm" && class(model) != "rma.mv": 'length(x) =
## 2 > 1' in coercion to 'logical(1)'
```

```
I2_CI
```

```
##          I2_Est. 2.5% CI 97.5% CI
## species  0.1786  0.1126  0.2514
## animal   0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## key      0.0761  0.0511  0.1051
## Group    0.0871  0.0683  0.1084
## obs      0.6451  0.5808  0.7079
## phylo    0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## Vt.VT    0.9869  0.9854  0.9884
```

```
#write.csv(I2_CI, "model output/I2_CI_meta_survival.csv")
```

```
# # same results could be obtained by using
# library(orchaRd)
# round(i2_ml(meta_survival),1)
```

4.2 Moderators

trait pairs

- survival-fertility (intercept)
- survival-growth
- survival-maturation
- survival-size

pvalues reported in Supp Table 1 (comparisons to intercept (survival-fertility) in the summary, pvalues for other comparisons with linearHypothesis)

```
meta_survival_pair <- update(meta_survival, ~. +pair)
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_pair)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##   logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -467.3060  934.6120  952.6120  991.2195  952.9523
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0595 0.2440   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0000   37    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0293 0.1712   58    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0309 0.1758  161    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2358 0.4856  543    no    obs    no
```

```

##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 539) = 23411.9494, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:4):
## QM(df = 3) = 2.0248, p-val = 0.5673
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.2162  0.0736   2.9389  0.0033   0.0720  0.3603  **
## pairsurvival-growth    0.0082  0.1351   0.0606  0.9517  -0.2567  0.2730
## pairsurvival-maturation -0.0912  0.0689  -1.3249  0.1852  -0.2262  0.0437
## pairsurvival-size     -0.0183  0.0780  -0.2347  0.8145  -0.1713  0.1346
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_pair)
```

```

##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.003870105    0.339385639

```

```

#save(meta_survival_pair, file = "model/meta_survival_pair.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_pair), file = "model output/meta_survival_pair.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_pair), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_pair.csv")

```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_pair, c(0,1,-1,0))
```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairsurvival - growth - pairsurvival - maturation = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##      Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1         540
## 2         539  1 0.5204    0.4707

```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_pair, c(0,1,0,-1))
```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairsurvival - growth - pairsurvival - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##      Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)

```

```
## 1    540
## 2    539  1 0.037    0.8475
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_pair, c(0,0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairsurvival - maturation - pairsurvival - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      540
## 2      539  1 0.9169    0.3383
```

```
meta_survival_lab <- update(meta_survival, ~. +lab_field)
```

lab vs field - survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_lab)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -468.1275  936.2551  950.2551  980.3090  950.4652
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim   sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor   R
## sigma^2.1 0.0349 0.1867   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0526 0.2294   37    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0288 0.1696   58    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0334 0.1828  161    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2344 0.4842  543    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 541) = 23761.3561, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 1.1444, p-val = 0.2847
##
## Model Results:
##
```

```
##           estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.0299  0.2260  0.1323  0.8948  -0.4130  0.4728
## lab_fielddlab    0.2522  0.2358  1.0698  0.2847  -0.2099  0.7144
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_lab)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.01392674    0.39813343
```

```
#save(meta_survival_lab, file = "model/meta_survival_lab.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_lab), file = "model output/meta_survival_lab.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_lab), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_lab.csv")
```

```
meta_survival_sex <- update(meta_survival, ~. +sex)
```

sex (males, females, both) - survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_sex)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -467.9892   935.9784   951.9784   986.3110   952.2496
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0755 0.2748   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0001   37    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0210 0.1451   58    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0315 0.1774  161    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2358 0.4856  543    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 540) = 23797.8894, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 0.9157, p-val = 0.6326
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
```

```
## intrcpt      0.1403  0.0849  1.6540  0.0981  -0.0260  0.3067  .
## sexfemale    0.0863  0.0909  0.9499  0.3422  -0.0918  0.2644
## sexmale      0.0514  0.1181  0.4351  0.6635  -0.1800  0.2828
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_sex)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.004154573    0.354540590
```

```
#save(meta_survival_sex, file = "model/meta_survival_sex.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_sex), file = "model output/meta_survival_sex.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_sex), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_sex.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_sex, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## sexfemale - sexmale = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~sex
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     541
## 2     540  1 0.1197    0.7293
```

```
meta_survival_stage <- update(meta_survival, ~. +stage)
```

life stages - survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
# be aware that there is no data for the level adult and that's the reason for:
# Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
# table(survival_pair_data$stage)
summary(meta_survival_stage)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##   logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -468.4246  936.8493  952.8493  987.1818  953.1205
```

```

##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0671 0.2590   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0001   37    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0312 0.1766   58    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0310 0.1760  161    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2346 0.4844  543    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 540) = 23604.9239, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 0.3422, p-val = 0.8427
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt      0.2333  0.1004  2.3232  0.0202   0.0365  0.4301 *
## stageboth   -0.0839  0.2341 -0.3585  0.7199  -0.5428  0.3749
## stagecross  -0.0512  0.0911 -0.5614  0.5745  -0.2298  0.1275
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_stage)
```

```

##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.0009191877  0.3557506658

```

```

#save(meta_survival_stage, file = "model/meta_survival_stage.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_stage), file = "model output/meta_survival_stage.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_stage), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_stage.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_stage, c(0,1,-1))

```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stageboth - stagecross = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     541
## 2     540  1 0.0226    0.8805

```

```
meta_survival_design <- update(meta_survival, ~. +Design_rename)
```

experimental design - survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There  
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_design)
```

```
##  
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)  
##  
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc  
## -466.8771  933.7541  949.7541  984.0867  950.0253  
##  
## Variance Components:  
##  
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R  
## sigma^2.1 0.0345 0.1859   37    no  species  no  
## sigma^2.2 0.0492 0.2218   37    no   animal  yes  
## sigma^2.3 0.0297 0.1724   58    no     key   no  
## sigma^2.4 0.0332 0.1822  161    no   Group  no  
## sigma^2.5 0.2344 0.4841  543    no     obs   no  
##  
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:  
## QE(df = 540) = 23808.8691, p-val < .0001  
##  
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):  
## QM(df = 2) = 2.1679, p-val = 0.3383  
##  
## Model Results:  
##  
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub  
## intrcpt              0.2843  0.1485   1.9147  0.0555  -0.0067  0.5754  
## Design_renamegenotype -0.0619  0.1181  -0.5245  0.5999  -0.2934  0.1695  
## Design_renamepedigree -0.2655  0.1810  -1.4669  0.1424  -0.6202  0.0892  
##  
## ---  
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_design)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional  
##      0.0109826      0.3916536
```

```
#save(meta_survival_design, file = "model/meta_survival_design.RData")  
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_design), file = "model output/meta_survival_design.csv")  
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_design), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_design.csv")  
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_design, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test  
##  
## Hypothesis:  
## Design_renamegenotype - Design_renamepedigree = 0
```

```
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~Design_rename
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     541
## 2     540  1 1.1842    0.2765
```

```
meta_survival_narrow <- update(meta_survival, ~. +narrow_broad)
```

narrow vs broad sense correlation - survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_narrow)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -468.8505  937.7010  951.7010  981.7550  951.9112
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0660  0.2568    37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000  0.0001    37    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0296  0.1721    58    no     key   no
## sigma^2.4 0.0313  0.1770   161    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2347  0.4845   543    no     obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 541) = 23789.0694, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 0.0000, p-val = 0.9946
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.1895  0.0769   2.4632  0.0138   0.0387  0.3404 *
## narrow_broadnarrow -0.0006  0.0913  -0.0067  0.9946  -0.1796  0.1783
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_narrow)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional  
##      2.451794e-07  3.509786e-01
```

```
#save(meta_survival_narrow, file = "model/meta_survival_narrow.RData")  
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_narrow), file = "model output/meta_survival_narrow.csv")  
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_narrow), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_narrow.csv")
```

```
meta_survival_pair_removeint <- update(meta_survival_pair, ~. -1)
```

REPORT meta-analytic means for each set of moderators (reported in Supp Tables 1 & 3)

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~pair - 1, random =  
## list(~1 | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which  
## there are no data.
```

```
meta_survival_lab_removeint <- update(meta_survival_lab, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~lab_field - :  
## There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no  
## data.
```

```
meta_survival_sex_removeint <- update(meta_survival_sex, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~sex - 1, random =  
## list(~1 | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which  
## there are no data.
```

```
meta_survival_stage_removeint <- update(meta_survival_stage, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~stage - 1, : There  
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
meta_survival_design_removeint <- update(meta_survival_design, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~Design_rename - :  
## There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no  
## data.
```

```
meta_survival_narrow_removeint <- update(meta_survival_narrow, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~narrow_broad - :
## There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no
## data.
```

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~narrow_broad - :
## Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
model <- c("meta_survival_pair_removeint", "meta_survival_lab_removeint",
          "meta_survival_sex_removeint", "meta_survival_stage_removeint", "meta_survival_design_removeint")

coeff <- list()
roundup <- list()
for (i in model) {
  roundup[[i]] <- coef(summary(get(i))) %>% mutate_if(is.numeric, round, 2)
  coeff[[i]] <- roundup[[i]]
coeff[[i]] <- cbind(rownames(coeff[[i]]), data.frame(coeff[[i]], row.names=NULL))
names(coeff[[i]])[1] <- "var"
}
coeff
```

```
## $meta_survival_pair_removeint
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 pairsurvival-fertility 0.22 0.07 2.94 0.00 0.07 0.36
## 2 pairsurvival-growth    0.22 0.13 1.66 0.10 -0.04 0.49
## 3 pairsurvival-maturation 0.12 0.08 1.61 0.11 -0.03 0.28
## 4 pairsurvival-size      0.20 0.08 2.47 0.01 0.04 0.35
##
## $meta_survival_lab_removeint
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 lab_fieldfield 0.03 0.23 0.13 0.89 -0.41 0.47
## 2 lab_fieldlab 0.28 0.15 1.84 0.07 -0.02 0.58
##
## $meta_survival_sex_removeint
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 sexboth 0.14 0.08 1.65 0.10 -0.03 0.31
## 2 sexfemale 0.23 0.08 2.96 0.00 0.08 0.38
## 3 sexmale 0.19 0.11 1.76 0.08 -0.02 0.41
##
## $meta_survival_stage_removeint
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 stageboth 0.15 0.22 0.67 0.50 -0.28 0.58
## 2 stagecross 0.18 0.07 2.71 0.01 0.05 0.31
## 3 stagenon_adult 0.23 0.10 2.32 0.02 0.04 0.43
##
## $meta_survival_design_removeint
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 Design_renamefamily 0.28 0.15 1.91 0.06 -0.01 0.58
## 2 Design_renamegenotype 0.22 0.16 1.40 0.16 -0.09 0.53
## 3 Design_renamepedigree 0.02 0.20 0.10 0.92 -0.37 0.41
##
## $meta_survival_narrow_removeint
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 narrow_broadbroad 0.19 0.08 2.46 0.01 0.04 0.34
## 2 narrow_broadnarrow 0.19 0.08 2.32 0.02 0.03 0.35
```

```
#capture.output(coeff, file="model output/coeff_survival_mod_withoutintercept.csv")
```

5. Non-survival pairs

5.1 intercept only model

```
meta_other <- rma.mv(zr_sign, raw_vi, random= list(~ 1|species, ~ 1|animal, ~ 1|key, ~1|Group, ~1|obs),  
  R= list(animal = tree_matrix),  
  data = other_pair_data, method= "REML")
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(zr_sign, raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, ~1 | animal, :  
## There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no  
## data.
```

```
summary(meta_other)
```

```
##  
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)  
##  
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc  
## -707.1838  1414.3675  1426.3675  1454.5645  1426.4719  
##  
## Variance Components:  
##  
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R  
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0001   82    no  species  no  
## sigma^2.2 0.0397 0.1992   82    no  animal  yes  
## sigma^2.3 0.1240 0.3521  108    no    key  no  
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  269    no  Group  no  
## sigma^2.5 0.2428 0.4927  813    no    obs  no  
##  
## Test for Heterogeneity:  
## Q(df = 812) = 430354.2615, p-val < .0001  
##  
## Model Results:  
##  
## estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub  
##  0.1081  0.1200  0.9013  0.3674  -0.1270  0.3433  
##  
## ---  
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
predict(meta_other)
```

```
##  
##      pred      se      ci.lb      ci.ub      pi.lb      pi.ub  
##  0.1081  0.1200  -0.1270  0.3433  -1.1634  1.3796
```

```

#capture.output(summary(meta_other), file = "model output/meta_other.csv")
#save(meta_other, file = "model/meta_other.RData")
#calculate I2
I2_CI <- I2(meta_other, other_pair_data$raw_vi , ME = FALSE, sims = 10000, phylo = "animal", obs = "obs")

```

```

## Warning in class(model) != "MCMCglmm" && class(model) != "rma.mv": 'length(x) =
## 2 > 1' in coercion to 'logical(1)'

```

```

## Warning in class(model) != "MCMCglmm" && class(model) != "rma.mv": 'length(x) =
## 2 > 1' in coercion to 'logical(1)'

```

```
I2_CI
```

```

##           I2_Est. 2.5% CI 97.5% CI
## species  0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## animal   0.0974  0.0709  0.1274
## key      0.3041  0.2460  0.3632
## Group    0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## obs      0.5968  0.5410  0.6520
## phylo    0.0975  0.0711  0.1276
## Vt.VT    0.9982  0.9981  0.9984

```

```

#write.csv(I2_CI, "model output/I2_CI_meta_other.csv")
# # same results could be obtained by using
# library(orchard)
# round(i2_ml(meta_other),1)

```

5.2 Moderators

```
meta_other_pair <- update(meta_other, ~. +pair)
```

trait pairs - non-survival pairs

```

## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.

```

```
summary(meta_other_pair)
```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##   logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -693.0243 1386.0486 1408.0486 1459.6752 1408.3807
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0001    82    no  species  no

```

```

## sigma^2.2  0.0200  0.1414    82    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3  0.1203  0.3468   108    no    key   no
## sigma^2.4  0.0000  0.0000   269    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5  0.2395  0.4894   813    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 807) = 416218.0231, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:6):
## QM(df = 5) = 22.8031, p-val = 0.0004
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.1932  0.1027   1.8806  0.0600  -0.0082  0.3946
## pairgrowth-fertility  -0.1411  0.1974  -0.7147  0.4748  -0.5280  0.2458
## pairgrowth-maturation  0.1670  0.1215   1.3749  0.1692  -0.0711  0.4052
## pairgrowth-size       -0.0376  0.1005  -0.3742  0.7082  -0.2345  0.1593
## pairmaturation-fertility -0.0052  0.0757  -0.0683  0.9456  -0.1535  0.1432
## pairmaturation-size   -0.2204  0.0696  -3.1654  0.0015  -0.3569 -0.0839
##
## intrcpt              .
## pairgrowth-fertility
## pairgrowth-maturation
## pairgrowth-size
## pairmaturation-fertility
## pairmaturation-size   **
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_pair)
```

```

##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.0347510    0.3913128

```

```

#save(meta_other_pair, file = "model/meta_other_pair.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_pair), file = "model output/meta_other_pair.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_pair), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_pair.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,-1,0,0,0))

```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairgrowth - maturation = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      808
## 2      807  1 2.0596    0.1513

```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,0,-1,0,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairgrowth - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 0.2592    0.6107
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,0,0,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairmaturation - fertility = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 0.4609    0.4972
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,0,0,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 0.1646    0.685
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,1,-1,0,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - maturation - pairgrowth - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
```

```
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 3.3116 0.06879 .
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,1,0,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - maturation - pairmaturation - fertility = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 1.9006 0.168
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,1,0,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - maturation - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 12.628 0.0003801 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,0,1,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - size - pairmaturation - fertility = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 0.0949 0.758
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,0,1,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - size - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 4.6638    0.0308 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,0,0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairmaturation - fertility - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 8.4329    0.003685 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
meta_other_lab <- update(meta_other, ~. +lab_field)
```

lab vs field - non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_lab)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -704.6888 1409.3777 1423.3777 1456.2656 1423.5172
##
## Variance Components:
```

```

##
##          estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000  0.0000    82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0420  0.2050    82    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.1190  0.3449   108    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000  0.0000   269    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2431  0.4930   813    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 811) = 430210.2192, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 2.1470, p-val = 0.1429
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.3318  0.1956   1.6964  0.0898  -0.0515  0.7151
## lab_fieldlab    -0.2519  0.1719  -1.4652  0.1429  -0.5889  0.0851
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_lab)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.01806442      0.40928406
```

```

#save(meta_other_lab, file = "model/meta_other_lab.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_lab), file = "model output/meta_other_lab.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_lab), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_lab.csv")

```

```
meta_other_sex <- update(meta_other, ~. +sex, control=list(rel.tol=1e-8))
```

sex (males, females, both) - non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_sex)
```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -703.6603  1407.3206  1423.3206  1460.8969  1423.5004
##
## Variance Components:
##

```

```

##          estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed   factor    R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000  0.0007    82    no  species   no
## sigma^2.2 0.0285  0.1688    82    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.1242  0.3524   108    no     key   no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000  0.0001   269    no   Group   no
## sigma^2.5 0.2428  0.4927   813    no     obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 810) = 430209.1142, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 3.7671, p-val = 0.1521
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt      0.1184  0.1138   1.0400  0.2983  -0.1047  0.3415
## sexfemale    0.0179  0.0834   0.2149  0.8299  -0.1455  0.1813
## sexmale     -0.1507  0.1073  -1.4049  0.1601  -0.3609  0.0595
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_sex)
```

```

##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.006605022    0.390144685

```

```

#save(meta_other_sex, file = "model/meta_other_sex.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_sex), file = "model output/meta_other_sex.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_sex), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_sex.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_sex, c(0,1,-1))

```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## sexfemale - sexmale = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~sex
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      811
## 2      810  1 3.7284    0.0535 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
meta_other_stage <- update(meta_other, ~. +stage)
```

life stages - non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_stage)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -701.4780 1402.9561 1420.9561 1463.2183 1421.1814
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000    82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0492 0.2219    82    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.1108 0.3329   108    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000   269    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2431 0.4931   813    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 809) = 428282.0382, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:4):
## QM(df = 3) = 7.8188, p-val = 0.0499
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.2168 0.1423  1.5229 0.1278 -0.0622  0.4958
## stageboth        -0.0370 0.1271 -0.2911 0.7710 -0.2862  0.2122
## stagecross       -0.1594 0.0683 -2.3338 0.0196 -0.2933 -0.0255 *
## stagenon_adult  -0.0556 0.0966 -0.5759 0.5647 -0.2449  0.1336
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_stage)
```

```
##   R2_marginal R2_conditional
##   0.01041396  0.40326968
```

```
#save(meta_other_stage, file = "model/meta_other_stage.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_stage), file = "model output/meta_other_stage.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_stage), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_stage.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_stage, c(0,1,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stageboth - stagecross = 0
##
```

```
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     810
## 2     809  1 1.2841     0.2571
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_stage, c(0,1,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stageboth - stagenon_adult = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     810
## 2     809  1 0.0199     0.8878
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_stage, c(0,0, 1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stagecross - stagenon_adult = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     810
## 2     809  1 1.8272     0.1765
```

```
meta_other_design <- update(meta_other, ~. +Design_rename)
```

experimental design - non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_design)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
```

```

## -703.0290 1406.0579 1422.0579 1459.6342 1422.2377
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000   82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0414 0.2035   82    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.1218 0.3490  108    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  269    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2427 0.4927   813   no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 810) = 429953.8822, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 3.1520, p-val = 0.2068
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb  ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.0587  0.1290  0.4552  0.6490  -0.1941  0.3115
## Design_renamegenotype  0.0453  0.1173  0.3865  0.6991  -0.1845  0.2752
## Design_renamepedigree  0.2617  0.1483  1.7651  0.0776  -0.0289  0.5523 .
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_design)
```

```

##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.01848721    0.41319558

```

```

#save(meta_other_design, file = "model/meta_other_design.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_design), file = "model output/meta_other_design.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_design), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_design.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_design, c(0,1,-1))

```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## Design_renamegenotype - Design_renamepedigree = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~Design_rename
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      811
## 2      810  1 1.4693    0.2255

```

```
meta_other_narrow <- update(meta_other, ~. +narrow_broad)
```

narrow vs broad genetic correlation - non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Rows with NAs omitted from model fitting.
```

```
summary(meta_other_narrow)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 812; method: REML)
##
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -702.9598  1405.9196  1421.9196  1459.4860  1422.0996
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0000    82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2  0.0560  0.2366    82    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3  0.1229  0.3506   107    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4  0.0000  0.0000   268    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5  0.2420  0.4920   812    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 809) = 430333.1847, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 1.0966, p-val = 0.5779
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se  zval  pval  ci.lb  ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.0661  0.1446  0.4573  0.6474 -0.2173  0.3496
## narrow_broaddominance  0.0398  0.2476  0.1609  0.8722 -0.4455  0.5252
## narrow_broadnarrow    0.0931  0.0901  1.0325  0.3018 -0.0836  0.2697
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_narrow)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.005041315    0.427938777
```

```
#save(meta_other_narrow, file = "model/meta_other_narrow.RData")
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_narrow), file = "model output/meta_other_narrow.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_narrow), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_narrow.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_narrow, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
```

```
##
## Hypothesis:
## narrow_broaddominance - narrow_broadnarrow = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~narrow_broad
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     810
## 2     809  1 0.0512    0.8209
```

```
meta_other_pair_removeint <- update(meta_other_pair, ~. -1)
```

REPORT meta-analytic means for moderators for non-survival pairs (reported in Supp Tables 2 & 4)

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~pair - 1, random = list(~1
## | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are
## no data.
```

```
meta_other_lab_removeint <- update(meta_other_lab, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~lab_field - 1, random =
## list(~1 | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which
## there are no data.
```

```
meta_other_sex_removeint <- update(meta_other_sex, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~sex - 1, random = list(~1 |
## : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no
## data.
```

```
meta_other_stage_removeint <- update(meta_other_stage, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~stage - 1, random = list(~1
## | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are
## no data.
```

```
meta_other_design_removeint <- update(meta_other_design, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~Design_rename - 1, random =
## list(~1 | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which
## there are no data.
```

```
meta_other_narrow_removeint <- update(meta_other_narrow, ~. -1)
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, mods = ~narrow_broad - 1, random =
## list(~1 | : There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which
## there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Rows with NAs omitted from model fitting.
```

```
model <- c("meta_other_pair_removeint", "meta_other_lab_removeint",
          "meta_other_sex_removeint", "meta_other_stage_removeint", "meta_other_design_removeint", "meta_other_narrow_removeint")

coeff <- list()
roundup <- list()
for (i in model) {
  roundup[[i]] <- coef(summary(get(i))) %>% mutate_if(is.numeric, round, 2)
  coeff[[i]] <- roundup[[i]]
  coeff[[i]] <- cbind(rownames(coeff[[i]]), data.frame(coeff[[i]], row.names=NULL))
  names(coeff[[i]][1]) <- "var"
}
coeff
```

```
## $meta_other_pair_removeint
##           var estimate  se  zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 pairfertility-size  0.19 0.10  1.88 0.06 -0.01  0.39
## 2 pairgrowth-fertility  0.05 0.21  0.25 0.80 -0.35  0.46
## 3 pairgrowth-maturation  0.36 0.14  2.65 0.01  0.09  0.63
## 4 pairgrowth-size  0.16 0.12  1.31 0.19 -0.08  0.39
## 5 pairmaturation-fertility  0.19 0.11  1.75 0.08 -0.02  0.40
## 6 pairmaturation-size -0.03 0.10 -0.28 0.78 -0.22  0.16
##
## $meta_other_lab_removeint
##           var estimate  se  zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 lab_fieldfield  0.33 0.20  1.70 0.09 -0.05  0.72
## 2 lab_fieldlab  0.08 0.12  0.64 0.52 -0.16  0.32
##
## $meta_other_sex_removeint
##           var estimate  se  zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 sexboth  0.12 0.11  1.04 0.30 -0.10  0.34
## 2 sexfemale  0.14 0.11  1.20 0.23 -0.09  0.36
## 3 sexmale -0.03 0.13 -0.25 0.80 -0.29  0.22
##
## $meta_other_stage_removeint
##           var estimate  se  zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 stageadult  0.22 0.14  1.52 0.13 -0.06  0.50
## 2 stageboth  0.18 0.17  1.06 0.29 -0.15  0.51
## 3 stagecross  0.06 0.13  0.43 0.66 -0.20  0.32
## 4 stagenon_adult  0.16 0.14  1.12 0.26 -0.12  0.44
##
## $meta_other_design_removeint
##           var estimate  se  zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 Design_renamefamily  0.06 0.13  0.46 0.65 -0.19  0.31
## 2 Design_renamegenotype  0.10 0.15  0.70 0.48 -0.19  0.39
## 3 Design_renamepedigree  0.32 0.18  1.81 0.07 -0.03  0.67
##
## $meta_other_narrow_removeint
```

```
##           var estimate   se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## 1 narrow_broadbroad    0.07 0.14 0.46 0.65 -0.22 0.35
## 2 narrow_broaddominance 0.11 0.27 0.39 0.70 -0.43 0.64
## 3 narrow_broadnarrow   0.16 0.15 1.08 0.28 -0.13 0.45
```

```
#capture.output(coeff, file="model output/coeff_other_mod_withoutintercept.csv")
```

6. Publication bias

6.1. sample size effects

```
#survival pairs
survival_pair_data$se <- sqrt(survival_pair_data$raw_vi)
meta_survival_se <- update(meta_survival, ~. + se)
```

survival-pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
#save(meta_survival_se, file = "model/meta_survival_se.RData")
summary(meta_survival_se)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -467.9306  935.8612  949.8612  979.9152  950.0714
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0524 0.2288   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0001   37    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0370 0.1923   58    no     key   no
## sigma^2.4 0.0297 0.1723  161    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2354 0.4852  543    no     obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 541) = 23814.2633, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 1.7470, p-val = 0.1863
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se   zval   pval   ci.lb  ci.ub
## intrcpt    0.1130 0.0848  1.3324 0.1827 -0.0532 0.2793
## se         0.4219 0.3192  1.3217 0.1863 -0.2037 1.0475
```

```
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_se)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.01144173    0.34343861
```

```
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_se), file = "model output/meta_survival_se.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_se), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_se.csv")
```

```
#other pairs
other_pair_data$se <- sqrt(other_pair_data$raw_vi)
meta_other_se <- update(meta_other, ~. + se)
```

non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
#save(meta_other_se, file = "model/meta_other_se.RData")
summary(meta_other_se)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -704.9546  1409.9091  1423.9091  1456.7970  1424.0486
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0000    82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2  0.0505  0.2248    82    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3  0.1202  0.3467   108    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4  0.0000  0.0000   269    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5  0.2430  0.4929   813    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 811) = 430350.4325, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 2.0792, p-val = 0.1493
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt      0.1933  0.1448   1.3353  0.1818  -0.0904  0.4771
```

```
## se      -0.4480  0.3107  -1.4419  0.1493  -1.0569  0.1609
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_se)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.0111613      0.4192743
```

```
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_se), file = "model output/meta_other_se.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_se), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_se.csv")
```

6.2 decline effects (publication year effects)

```
#survival pairs
meta_survival_year <- update(meta_survival, ~. + scale(pub_year))
```

survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
#save(meta_survival_year, file = "model/meta_survival_year.RData")
summary(meta_survival_year)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -468.2953  936.5905   950.5905   980.6445   950.8007
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0712 0.2668   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0001   37    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0239 0.1546   58    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0311 0.1763  161    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2348 0.4846  543    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 541) = 23810.4610, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 1.1967, p-val = 0.2740
##
## Model Results:
##
```

```
##           estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.1815  0.0652  2.7859  0.0053  0.0538  0.3093 **
## scale(pub_year)   0.0469  0.0429  1.0940  0.2740 -0.0371  0.1310
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_year)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.006058082    0.353429554
```

```
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_year), file = "model output/meta_survival_year.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_year), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_year.csv")
```

```
#other pairs
meta_other_year <- update(meta_other, ~. + scale(pub_year))
```

non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
#save(meta_other_year, file = "model/meta_other_year.RData")
summary(meta_other_year)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 813; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -705.0459  1410.0919  1424.0919  1456.9797  1424.2313
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0001   82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2  0.0305  0.1748   82    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3  0.1287  0.3587  108    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4  0.0000  0.0000  269    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5  0.2423  0.4922  813    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 811) = 430155.7615, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 2.0305, p-val = 0.1542
##
## Model Results:
##
```

```
##           estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.0990  0.1082  0.9150  0.3602  -0.1131  0.3112
## scale(pub_year)   0.0632  0.0443  1.4249  0.1542  -0.0237  0.1500
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_year)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.009836951    0.402545965
```

```
#capture.output(summary(meta_other_year), file = "model output/meta_other_year.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_year), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_year.csv")
```

6.3 all-in models

```
#survival
```

```
meta_survival_all_in <- update(meta_survival, ~. +pair + lab_field + sex + stage + Design_rename + narrow)
```

survival pairs

```
## Warning in metafor::rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
#save(meta_survival_all_in, file = "model/meta_survival_all_in.RData")
summary(meta_survival_all_in)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 543; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -453.5375   907.0749   945.0749  1026.2237  946.5681
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0187 0.1369   37    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.1491 0.3861   37    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0171 0.1309   58    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0315 0.1775  161    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2372 0.4871  543    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 529) = 22833.6761, p-val < .0001
##
```

```

## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:14):
## QM(df = 13) = 15.0862, p-val = 0.3020
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.1022  0.3744   0.2729  0.7849  -0.6316  0.8359
## pairsurvival-growth -0.0032  0.1727  -0.0183  0.9854  -0.3416  0.3353
## pairsurvival-maturation -0.1262  0.0766  -1.6471  0.0995  -0.2764  0.0240
## pairsurvival-size     0.0044  0.0853   0.0517  0.9587  -0.1627  0.1715
## lab_fieldlab         0.1977  0.3017   0.6553  0.5123  -0.3937  0.7891
## sexfemale           0.1858  0.1019   1.8239  0.0682  -0.0139  0.3855
## sexmale             0.1659  0.1253   1.3246  0.1853  -0.0796  0.4114
## stageboth          -0.3374  0.2747  -1.2282  0.2194  -0.8759  0.2010
## stagecross         -0.1599  0.1078  -1.4830  0.1381  -0.3712  0.0514
## Design_renamegenotype -0.1987  0.1517  -1.3097  0.1903  -0.4960  0.0986
## Design_renamepedigree -0.2420  0.2005  -1.2071  0.2274  -0.6349  0.1509
## narrow_broadnarrow    0.0722  0.1133   0.6367  0.5243  -0.1500  0.2943
## se                  0.5757  0.3821   1.5066  0.1319  -0.1733  1.3247
## scale(pub_year)      0.0772  0.0429   1.7978  0.0722  -0.0070  0.1613
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_all_in)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.05808472      0.50749764
```

```

#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_all_in), file = "model output/meta_survival_all_in.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_all_in), file = "model output/R2_meta_survival_all_in.csv")

```

```
#other traits
```

```
meta_other_all_in <- update(meta_other, ~. +pair + lab_field + sex + stage + Design_rename + narrow_broad)
```

non-survival pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = raw_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Rows with NAs omitted from model fitting.
```

```

#save(meta_other_all_in, file = "model/meta_other_all_in.RData")
summary(meta_other_all_in)

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 812; method: REML)
##

```

```

##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -674.8424 1349.6847 1395.6847 1503.2577 1397.1185
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0001   82    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0430 0.2075   82    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.1077 0.3282  107    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  268    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.2400 0.4899   812    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 794) = 414604.6208, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:18):
## QM(df = 17) = 34.9842, p-val = 0.0063
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.4486 0.2459   1.8241  0.0681  -0.0334  0.9305
## pairgrowth-fertility -0.0773 0.2081  -0.3713  0.7104  -0.4851  0.3305
## pairgrowth-maturation  0.2003 0.1502   1.3338  0.1823  -0.0940  0.4946
## pairgrowth-size      -0.0780 0.1407  -0.5543  0.5794  -0.3538  0.1978
## pairmaturation-fertility 0.0829 0.1028   0.8064  0.4200  -0.1186  0.2845
## pairmaturation-size   -0.1400 0.1030  -1.3590  0.1742  -0.3418  0.0619
## lab_fieldlab         -0.1977 0.1767  -1.1185  0.2633  -0.5441  0.1487
## sexfemale            -0.0400 0.0927  -0.4321  0.6657  -0.2217  0.1416
## sexmale              -0.1545 0.1107  -1.3959  0.1628  -0.3715  0.0624
## stageboth           -0.0040 0.1737  -0.0230  0.9817  -0.3445  0.3365
## stagecross          -0.1504 0.0993  -1.5139  0.1301  -0.3450  0.0443
## stagenon_adult       0.0082 0.1337   0.0611  0.9513  -0.2539  0.2702
## Design_renamegenotype  0.0298 0.1264   0.2357  0.8137  -0.2179  0.2775
## Design_renamepedigree  0.0566 0.1622   0.3486  0.7274  -0.2614  0.3745
## narrow_broaddominance -0.0175 0.2508  -0.0698  0.9444  -0.5090  0.4740
## narrow_broadnarrow    0.0473 0.0988   0.4792  0.6318  -0.1463  0.2409
## se                   -0.2386 0.3592  -0.6643  0.5065  -0.9425  0.4654
## scale(pub_year)       0.0338 0.0446   0.7571  0.4490  -0.0536  0.1211
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_all_in)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.08138333      0.43577108
```

```

#capture.output(summary(meta_other_all_in), file = "model output/meta_other_all_in.csv")
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_all_in), file = "model output/R2_meta_other_all_in.csv")

```

7. Figures

load data

We can directly load the saved Rdata if we just want to update the figures (i.e. no need to re-run all the above code)

NB: I edited font size for k labels in Adobe when done as I could not figure out how to do it in the Orchard package directly!

```
# survival pair data
load("model/meta_survival.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_pair.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_lab.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_sex.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_stage.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_narrow.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_design.RData")

# non-survival pair data
load("model/meta_other.RData")
load("model/meta_other_pair.RData")
load("model/meta_other_lab.RData")
load("model/meta_other_sex.RData")
load("model/meta_other_stage.RData")
load("model/meta_other_narrow.RData")
load("model/meta_other_design.RData")

# pub bias data
load("model/meta_survival_se.RData")
load("model/meta_other_se.RData")
load("model/meta_survival_year.RData")
load("model/meta_other_year.RData")
```

Fig 2 - trait pairs

```
#pdf("figure_output/intercept_pair_230414.pdf", width=12, height=8, onefile=F)

survival_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival, mod = "1", group = "key", data = survival_pair,
                                     xlab = "",
                                     trunk.size = 2,
                                     branch.size = 1.5,
                                     fill = F)+
  scale_colour_manual(values = "purple") +
  ylim(-3.2, 3.7)

## Scale for colour is already present.
## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

survival_pair_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_pair, mod = "pair", group = "key", data = ,
                                     xlab = "",
                                     angle = 0,
```

```

        trunk.size = 2,
        branch.size = 1.5,
        fill = F) +
  theme(axis.text.y = element_text(size = 7)) +
  ylim(-3.2, 3.7)

other_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other, mod = "1", group = "key", data = other_pair_data),
  xlab = "Effect size (Zr)",
  trunk.size = 2,
  branch.size = 1.5,
  fill = F) +

  ylim(-3.2, 3.7) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = "orange")

## Scale for colour is already present.
## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

other_pair_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_pair, mod = "pair", group = "key", data = other_
  angle = 0,
  xlab = "Effect size (Zr)",
  trunk.size = 2,
  branch.size = 1.5,
  fill = F) +
  theme(axis.text.y = element_text(size = 7)) +
  ylim(-3.2, 3.7)

fig2 <- ggarrange(survival_plot, survival_pair_plot, other_plot, other_pair_plot, ncol = 2, nrow = 2,
  labels = c("(a)", "(b)", "(c)", "(d)"), common.legend = T)

fig2

```



```
#dev.off()

#ggsave("Fig2_pairs plot.pdf", plot = fig2, height = 150, width = 190, units = "mm", dpi = 600)
#ggsave("Fig2_pairs plot.png", plot = fig2, height = 150, width = 190, units = "mm", dpi = 600)
```

Fig 3 - moderators

```
#pdf("figure_output/moderators_both.pdf", width=12, height=12, onefile=F)
survival_lab_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_lab, mod = "lab_field", group = "key", data
                                angle = 0,
                                xlab = "",
                                trunk.size = 2,
                                branch.size = 1.5,
                                fill = F)+
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#d656ab", "#d656ab")) +
  ggtitle("(a) Correlations with survival") +
  ylim(-3, 3.7) +
  theme(plot.title = element_text(face="bold", size = 12))
```

```
## Scale for colour is already present.
## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.
```

```

survival_sex_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_sex, mod = "sex", group = "key", data = surv
                                angle = 0,
                                xlab = "",
                                trunk.size = 2,
                                branch.size = 1.5,
                                fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#cb56d6", "#cb56d6", "#cb56d6")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
 ## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

survival_stage_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_stage, mod = "stage", group = "key", data
                                angle = 0,
                                xlab = "",
                                trunk.size = 2,
                                branch.size = 1.5,
                                fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#8d56d6", "#8d56d6", "#8d56d6")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
 ## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

survival_design_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_design, mod = "Design_rename", group = "k
                                angle = 0,
                                xlab = "",
                                trunk.size = 2,
                                branch.size = 1.5,
                                fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#6956d6", "#6956d6", "#6956d6")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
 ## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

survival_narrow_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_narrow, mod = "narrow_broad", group = "k
                                angle = 0,
                                xlab = "Effect size (Zr)",
                                trunk.size = 2,
                                branch.size = 1.5,
                                fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#475fb3", "#475fb3")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
 ## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

other_lab_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_lab, mod = "lab_field", group = "key", data = other_lab_data),
  angle = 0,
  xlab = "",
  trunk.size = 2,
  branch.size = 1.5,
  fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#f76116", "#f76116")) +
  ggtitle("(b) Correlations among other LH traits") +
  ylim(-3, 3.7) +
  theme(plot.title = element_text(face="bold", size = 12))

```

Scale for colour is already present.
Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

other_sex_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_sex, mod = "sex", group = "key", data = other_sex_data),
  angle = 0,
  xlab = "",
  trunk.size = 2,
  branch.size = 1.5,
  fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#f78716", "#f78716", "#f78716")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

other_stage_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_stage, mod = "stage", group = "key", data = other_stage_data),
  angle = 0,
  xlab = "",
  trunk.size = 2,
  branch.size = 1.5,
  fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#f2ac16", "#f2ac16", "#f2ac16", "#f2ac16")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

other_design_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_design, mod = "Design_rename", group = "key", data = other_design_data),
  angle = 0,
  xlab = "",
  trunk.size = 2,
  branch.size = 1.5,
  fill = F) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("#f2d116", "#f2d116", "#f2d116")) +
  ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

Scale for colour is already present.
Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

other_narrow_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_narrow, mod = "narrow_broad", group = "key", d
                                angle = 0,
                                xlab = "Effect size (Zr)",
                                trunk.size = 2,
                                branch.size = 1.5,
                                fill = F) +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("#caf216", "#caf216", "#caf216")) +
ylim(-3, 3.7)

```

```

## Scale for colour is already present.
## Adding another scale for colour, which will replace the existing scale.

```

```

fig3 <- ggarrange(survival_lab_plot, other_lab_plot,
                  survival_sex_plot, other_sex_plot,
                  survival_stage_plot, other_stage_plot,
                  survival_design_plot, other_design_plot,
                  survival_narrow_plot, other_narrow_plot, nrow = 5, ncol = 2,
                  common.legend = T)

```

fig3


```

#ggsave("Fig3_moderators_plot.pdf", plot = fig3, height = 200, width = 140, unts = "mm", dpi = 600)
#ggsave("Fig3_moderators_plot.png", plot = fig3, height = 200, width = 190, unts = "mm", dpi = 600)

```

```
#dev.off()
```

Fig 4 - pub bias

```
egger_survival_se <- data.frame(se = survival_pair_data$se,
  zr_sign = survival_pair_data$zr_sign,
  pred = predict(meta_survival_se)$pred,
  upper = predict(meta_survival_se)$ci.ub,
  lower = predict(meta_survival_se)$ci.lb,
  Precision = sqrt(1/survival_pair_data$raw_vi))

egger_other_se <- data.frame(se = other_pair_data$se,
  zr_sign = other_pair_data$zr_sign,
  pred = predict(meta_other_se)$pred,
  upper = predict(meta_other_se)$ci.ub,
  lower = predict(meta_other_se)$ci.lb,
  Precision = sqrt(1/other_pair_data$raw_vi))

#pdf("figure_output/egger_se.pdf", width=8, height=6, onefile=F)

egger_se_survival_plot <- ggplot(egger_survival_se, aes(x = se, y = zr_sign)) +
  geom_point(aes(size = Precision), shape = 21, color = "#737372", fill = "#737372", alpha = 0.6) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = lower, ymax = upper, x = se), fill = "black", alpha=0.1) +
  geom_smooth(aes(y = pred, x = se), color = "black", size = 0.5) +
  labs(x = "Standard Error ", y = "Effect size (Zr)") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(axis.text.x= element_text(colour="black",
    size=13),
    axis.text.y= element_text( colour="black",
    size=13),
    axis.title.x = element_text(size=13),
    axis.title.y = element_text(size=13)) +
  ggtitle("(a) Correlations with survival") + theme(plot.title = element_text(face="bold", size = 12))

## Warning: Using 'size' aesthetic for lines was deprecated in ggplot2 3.4.0.
## i Please use 'linewidth' instead.
## This warning is displayed once every 8 hours.
## Call 'lifecycle::last_lifecycle_warnings()' to see where this warning was
## generated.
```

```
egger_se_other_plot <- ggplot(egger_other_se, aes(x = se, y = zr_sign)) +
  geom_point(aes(size = Precision), shape = 21, color = "#737372", fill = "#737372", alpha = 0.6) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = lower, ymax = upper, x = se), fill = "black", alpha=0.1) +
  geom_smooth(aes(y = pred, x = se), color = "black", size = 0.5) +
  labs(x = "Standard Error", y = "Effect size (Zr)") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(axis.text.x= element_text(colour="black",
    size=13),
    axis.text.y= element_text( colour="black",
    size=13),
    axis.title.x = element_text(size=13),
    axis.title.y = element_text(size=13)) +
  ggtitle("(b) Correlations among other LH traits") + theme(plot.title = element_text(face="bold", size
```

```

# year effects

year_survival <- data.frame(year = survival_pair_data$pub_year,
  zr_sign = survival_pair_data$zr_sign,
  raw_vi = survival_pair_data$raw_vi,
  pred = predict(meta_survival_year)$pred,
  upper = predict(meta_survival_year)$ci.ub,
  lower = predict(meta_survival_year)$ci.lb,
  Precision = sqrt(1/survival_pair_data$raw_vi))

year_other <- data.frame(year = other_pair_data$pub_year,
  zr_sign = other_pair_data$zr_sign,
  raw_vi = other_pair_data$raw_vi,
  pred = predict(meta_other_year)$pred,
  upper = predict(meta_other_year)$ci.ub,
  lower = predict(meta_other_year)$ci.lb,
  Precision = sqrt(1/other_pair_data$raw_vi))

#pdf("figure_output/year.pdf", width=8, height=6, onefile=F)

year_survival_plot <- ggplot(year_survival, aes(x = year, y = zr_sign)) +
  geom_point(aes(size = Precision),shape = 21, color = "#737372", fill = "#737372", alpha = 0.6) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = lower, ymax = upper, x = year), fill = "black", alpha=0.1) +
  geom_smooth(aes(y = pred, x = year), color = "black", size = 0.5) +
  labs(x = "Year", y = "Effect size (Zr)") +
  theme_bw() +
  scale_x_continuous(limits = c(1994, 2022), breaks = c(1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020)) +
  theme(axis.text.x= element_text(colour="black",
    size=12),
    axis.text.y= element_text( colour="black",
    size=13),
    axis.title.x = element_text(size=13),
    axis.title.y = element_text(size=13)) +
  ggtitle("(c)") + theme(plot.title = element_text(face="bold", size = 12))

year_other_plot <- ggplot(year_other, aes(x = year, y = zr_sign)) +
  geom_point(aes(size = Precision),shape = 21, color = "#737372", fill = "#737372", alpha = 0.6) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = lower, ymax = upper, x = year), fill = "black", alpha=0.1) +
  geom_smooth(aes(y = pred, x = year), color = "black", size = 0.5) +
  labs(x = "Year", y = "Effect size (Zr)") +
  theme_bw() +
  scale_x_continuous(limits = c(1994, 2022), breaks = c(1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020)) +
  theme(axis.text.x= element_text(colour="black",
    size=12),
    axis.text.y= element_text( colour="black",
    size=13),
    axis.title.x = element_text(size=13),
    axis.title.y = element_text(size=13)) +
  ggtitle("(d)") + theme(plot.title = element_text(face="bold", size = 12))

fig4 <- ggarrange(egger_se_survival_plot, egger_se_other_plot,
  year_survival_plot, year_other_plot, common.legend = T, ncol = 2, nrow = 2)

```

```
## 'geom_smooth()' using method = 'loess' and formula = 'y ~ x'
## 'geom_smooth()' using method = 'loess' and formula = 'y ~ x'
## 'geom_smooth()' using method = 'loess' and formula = 'y ~ x'
## 'geom_smooth()' using method = 'loess' and formula = 'y ~ x'
## 'geom_smooth()' using method = 'loess' and formula = 'y ~ x'
```

fig4


```
#ggsave("Fig4_se and year bias.pdf", plot = fig4, height = 200, width = 200, units = "mm", dpi = 600)
#ggsave("Fig4_se and year bias.png", plot = fig4, height = 200, width = 200, units = "mm", dpi = 600)
```

8. Sensitivity analysis

Studies often reported/used very different sample sizes. For example, studies using pedigree designs would report # of individuals which might be >1000 whereas family breeding designs might report families/genotypes with sample sizes closer to 10s. To investigate whether these larger sample sizes are unduly influencing our results we performed a sensitivity analysis where we natural-log transformed all reported sample sizes to bring them closer to the same scale and repeated all our analyses.

Bottom line: sample size differences do not largely influence our results numerically and have no effect on the qualitative interpretations.

These results are reported in our Supplementary Note and can be re-created using the below code.

8.1 Calculate Vi based on log transformed sample size

```
data_processed_full$log_vi <- 1/(log(data_processed_full$n, 2)-3)
summary(data_processed_full$log_vi)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
## -5.1909  0.1897  0.3285      Inf  0.6564      Inf
```

```
data_processed_full$obs <- 1:nrow(data_processed_full)
```

```
data_processed_full %>%
  group_by(Design_rename) %>%
  summarize(min = min(n),
            quant25 = quantile(n, probs = 0.25),
            quant50 = quantile(n, probs = 0.5),
            quant75 = quantile(n, probs = 0.75),
            max = max(n),
            n = length(n))
```

```
## # A tibble: 3 x 7
##   Design_rename  min quant25 quant50 quant75  max    n
##   <fct>          <int>  <dbl>   <dbl>  <dbl> <int> <int>
## 1 family           4     30     81    293 2372  927
## 2 genotype         4     10     19     43  100  743
## 3 pedigree       149    600   11742 15567 15996 216
```

```
data_processed_full %>%
  group_by(Design_rename) %>%
  summarize(min = min(log(n,2)),
            quant25 = quantile(log(n,2), probs = 0.25),
            quant50 = quantile(log(n,2), probs = 0.5),
            quant75 = quantile(log(n,2), probs = 0.75),
            max = max(log(n,2)),
            n = length(n))
```

```
## # A tibble: 3 x 7
##   Design_rename  min quant25 quant50 quant75  max    n
##   <fct>          <dbl>  <dbl>   <dbl>  <dbl> <dbl> <int>
## 1 family           2     4.91   6.34   8.19 11.2  927
## 2 genotype         2     3.32   4.25   5.43  6.64  743
## 3 pedigree       7.22   9.23  13.5   13.9 14.0  216
```

```
#remove data with negative or inf log_vi
```

```
data_processed_full_log <- data_processed_full[which(data_processed_full$log_vi > 0 & data_processed_full$log_vi < 10),]
summary(data_processed_full_log$log_vi)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##  0.0912  0.1948  0.3530  0.7095  0.6564  5.8849
```

```

data_log <- data_processed_full_log
survival_pair_data_log <- data_log[(data_log$trait_rename_1 == "survival" | data_log$trait_rename_2 == "survival") && !data_log$trait_rename_1 == "survival" | data_log$trait_rename_2 == "survival"]
other_pair_data_log <- data_log[!(data_log$trait_rename_1 == "survival" | data_log$trait_rename_2 == "survival")]

```

8.2 Survival pairs

```

meta_survival_log <- rma.mv(zr_sign, log_vi, random = list(~ 1|species, ~ 1|animal, ~ 1|key, ~ 1|Group, ~ 1|obs),
  R = list(animal = tree_matrix),
  data = survival_pair_data_log, method = "REML")

```

intercept only model

```

## Warning in rma.mv(zr_sign, log_vi, random = list(~ 1 | species, ~ 1 | animal, :
## There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no
## data.

```

```
summary(meta_survival_log)
```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)
##
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -459.5950   919.1900   931.1900   956.5492   931.3584
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0446 0.2112   33    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0000   33    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0084 0.0916   54    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0207 0.1439  150    no  Group    no
## sigma^2.5 0.0000 0.0001  507    no    obs    no
##
## Test for Heterogeneity:
## Q(df = 506) = 489.0086, p-val = 0.6982
##
## Model Results:
##
## estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## 0.1754 0.0590 2.9712 0.0030 0.0597 0.2911 **
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
predict(meta_survival_log)
```

```

##
##      pred      se ci.lb ci.ub pi.lb pi.ub
## 0.1754 0.0590 0.0597 0.2911 -0.3691 0.7199

```

```
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_log.csv")
#save(meta_survival_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival.RData")
#calculate I2
i2_ml(meta_survival_log)
```

```
##      I2_Total  I2_species  I2_animal      I2_key  I2_Group  I2_obs
## 1.935488e+01 1.171555e+01 1.898389e-11 2.201758e+00 5.437568e+00 3.238076e-06
```

```
#capture.output(i2_ml(meta_survival_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/I2_meta_survival.csv")
```

```
meta_survival_pair_log <- update(meta_survival_log, ~. +pair)
```

trait pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_pair_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -456.6133  913.2267   931.2267  969.2120  931.5918
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0391 0.1978   33    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0000   33    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0098 0.0991   54    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0199 0.1412  150    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.0000 0.0003  507    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 503) = 484.3597, p-val = 0.7170
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:4):
## QM(df = 3) = 2.3227, p-val = 0.5082
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.2044 0.0679   3.0085  0.0026   0.0712  0.3375 **
## pairsurvival-growth  0.0355 0.2001   0.1772  0.8593  -0.3567  0.4276
## pairsurvival-maturation -0.0983 0.0688  -1.4276  0.1534  -0.2332  0.0366
## pairsurvival-size    -0.0221 0.0805  -0.2746  0.7836  -0.1800  0.1358
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_pair_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional  
##      0.02507945    0.99999845
```

```
#save(meta_survival_pair_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_pair.RData")  
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_pair_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_pair_log.txt")  
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_pair_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_survival_pair_log.txt")
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_pair_log, c(0,1,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test  
##  
## Hypothesis:  
## pairsurvival - growth - pairsurvival - maturation = 0  
##  
## Model 1: restricted model  
## Model 2: ~pair  
##  
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)  
## 1     504  
## 2     503  1 0.4378    0.5082
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_pair_log, c(0,1,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test  
##  
## Hypothesis:  
## pairsurvival - growth - pairsurvival - size = 0  
##  
## Model 1: restricted model  
## Model 2: ~pair  
##  
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)  
## 1     504  
## 2     503  1 0.0799    0.7774
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_pair_log, c(0,0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test  
##  
## Hypothesis:  
## pairsurvival - maturation - pairsurvival - size = 0  
##  
## Model 1: restricted model  
## Model 2: ~pair  
##  
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)  
## 1     504  
## 2     503  1 0.9264    0.3358
```

```
meta_survival_lab_log <- update(meta_survival_log, ~. +lab_field, control=list(rel.tol=1e-8))
```

lab vs field

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There  
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_lab_log)
```

```
##  
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)  
##  
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc  
## -457.9833  915.9665   929.9665   959.5384   930.1919  
##  
## Variance Components:  
##  
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R  
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0008   33    no  species  no  
## sigma^2.2 0.0418 0.2045   33    no  animal  yes  
## sigma^2.3 0.0212 0.1457   54    no    key  no  
## sigma^2.4 0.0233 0.1527  150    no  Group  no  
## sigma^2.5 0.0000 0.0000  507    no    obs  no  
##  
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:  
## QE(df = 505) = 488.1848, p-val = 0.6964  
##  
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):  
## QM(df = 1) = 1.8563, p-val = 0.1731  
##  
## Model Results:  
##  
##      estimate      se     zval     pval     ci.lb     ci.ub  
## intrcpt      0.0008  0.1927  0.0044  0.9965  -0.3768  0.3785  
## lab_fieldlab  0.2871  0.2107  1.3625  0.1731  -0.1259  0.7001  
##  
## ---  
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_lab_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional  
##      0.07965974      1.00000000
```

```
#save(meta_survival_lab_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_lab.RData")  
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_lab_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_lab.  
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_lab_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_survival_lab
```

```
meta_survival_sex_log <- update(meta_survival_log, ~. +sex)
```

```
sex
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There  
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_sex_log)
```

```
##  
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)  
##  
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc  
## -458.1188   916.2376   932.2376   966.0182   932.5285  
##  
## Variance Components:  
##  
##      estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R  
## sigma^2.1  0.0564  0.2375    33    no  species  no  
## sigma^2.2  0.0000  0.0009    33    no  animal  yes  
## sigma^2.3  0.0038  0.0618    54    no    key  no  
## sigma^2.4  0.0203  0.1426   150    no  Group  no  
## sigma^2.5  0.0001  0.0096   507    no    obs  no  
##  
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:  
## QE(df = 504) = 488.4081, p-val = 0.6827  
##  
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):  
## QM(df = 2) = 0.5668, p-val = 0.7532  
##  
## Model Results:  
##  
##      estimate      se  zval  pval  ci.lb  ci.ub  
## intrcpt      0.1365  0.0833  1.6379  0.1014  -0.0268  0.2998  
## sexfemale    0.0650  0.0865  0.7514  0.4524  -0.1046  0.2346  
## sexmale      0.0471  0.1091  0.4319  0.6658  -0.1668  0.2610  
##  
## ---  
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_sex_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional  
##      0.01035696      0.99887358
```

```
#save(meta_survival_sex_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_sex.RData")  
#capture.output(summary(meta_survival_sex_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_sex.  
#capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_sex_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_survival_sex.  
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_sex_log, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## sexfemale - sexmale = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~sex
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     505
## 2     504  1 0.0335    0.8548
```

```
meta_survival_stage_log <- update(meta_survival_log, ~. +stage)
```

life stage

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_stage_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -457.7858  915.5716  931.5716  965.3522  931.8625
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0446 0.2111   33    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0000   33    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0087 0.0932   54    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0207 0.1439  150    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.0000 0.0002  507    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 504) = 488.3076, p-val = 0.6838
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 0.0860, p-val = 0.9579
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb  ci.ub
## intrcpt      0.1620  0.1019  1.5886  0.1121 -0.0379  0.3618
## stageboth    0.1143  0.4104  0.2785  0.7806 -0.6901  0.9188
## stagecross   0.0140  0.0941  0.1492  0.8814 -0.1704  0.1985
```

```
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_stage_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.003516053    0.999999372
```

```
# save(meta_survival_stage_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_stage.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_survival_stage_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_s
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_stage_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_survival_
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_stage_log, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stageboth - stagecross = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      505
## 2      504  1 0.0625    0.8025
```

```
meta_survival_design_log <- update(meta_survival_log, ~. +Design_rename)
```

experimental design

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_design_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)
##
##      logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -456.2602   912.5203   928.5203   962.3010   928.8113
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0530 0.2301   33    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0159 0.1261   33    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0000 0.0000   54    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0209 0.1445  150    no  Group  no
```

```
## sigma^2.5 0.0000 0.0001 507 no obs no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 504) = 487.5369, p-val = 0.6926
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 4.5701, p-val = 0.1018
##
## Model Results:
##
## estimate se zval pval ci.lb ci.ub
## intrcpt 0.2745 0.1028 2.6702 0.0076 0.0730 0.4760 **
## Design_renamegenotype -0.1260 0.0963 -1.3076 0.1910 -0.3148 0.0628
## Design_renamepedigree -0.2695 0.1333 -2.0214 0.0432 -0.5309 -0.0082 *
##
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_design_log)
```

```
## R2_marginal R2_conditional
## 0.06753598 0.99999989
```

```
# save(meta_survival_design_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_design.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_survival_design_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_design_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_survival_
linearHypothesis(meta_survival_design_log, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## Design_renamegenotype - Design_renamepedigree = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~Design_rename
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 505
## 2 504 1 1.0956 0.2952
```

```
meta_survival_narrow_log <- update(meta_survival_log, ~. + narrow_broad, control=list(optimizer="BFGS"))
```

narrow vs broad genetic correlation

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Redundant predictors dropped from the model.
```

```
summary(meta_survival_narrow_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 507; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -458.6792  917.3584  931.3584  960.9303  931.5837
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0051   33    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0000 0.0000   33    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0295 0.1718   54    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0218 0.1475  150    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.0000 0.0000  507    no    obs    no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 505) = 485.8833, p-val = 0.7218
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 0.7792, p-val = 0.3774
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.1952 0.0602   3.2405  0.0012   0.0771  0.3133  **
## narrow_broadnarrow -0.0717 0.0813  -0.8827  0.3774  -0.2311  0.0876
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_survival_narrow_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.02364138      1.00000000
```

```
# save(meta_survival_narrow_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_narrow.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_survival_narrow_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_survival_narrow_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_survival_
```

```
#load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival.RData")
class(meta_survival_log) <- "rma.mv"
I2_CI <- I2(meta_survival_log, survival_pair_data_log$log_vi , ME = FALSE, sims = 10000, phylo = "anima
I2_CI
```

calculate I2

```
##          I2_Est. 2.5% CI 97.5% CI
## species  0.1162  0.0701  0.1711
## animal   0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## key      0.0221  0.0146  0.0311
## Group    0.0543  0.0429  0.0666
## obs      0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## phylo    0.0000  0.0000  0.0000
## Vt.VT    0.1926  0.1477  0.2438
```

```
# write.csv(I2_CI, "model output/sensitivity_log/I2_CI_meta_survival.csv")
```

8.3 non-survival pairs

```
meta_other_log <- rma.mv(zr_sign, log_vi, random= list(~ 1|species, ~ 1|animal, ~ 1|key, ~1|Group, ~1|obs),
  R= list(animal = tree_matrix),
  data = other_pair_data_log, method= "REML")
```

intercept only model

```
## Warning in rma.mv(zr_sign, log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, ~1 | animal, :
## There are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no
## data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 764; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -736.4579  1472.9159  1484.9159  1512.7394  1485.0270
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0000    75    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2  0.0498  0.2232    75    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3  0.0197  0.1405   100    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4  0.0000  0.0000   244    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5  0.0778  0.2790   764    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Heterogeneity:
## Q(df = 763) = 884.2434, p-val = 0.0015
##
## Model Results:
##
## estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
##  0.1266  0.1288  0.9830  0.3256  -0.1258  0.3790
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
predict(meta_other_log)
```

```
##  
##   pred      se   ci.lb  ci.ub  pi.lb  pi.ub  
## 0.1266 0.1288 -0.1258 0.3790 -0.6671 0.9202
```

```
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other.csv")  
# save(meta_other_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other.RData")  
#calculate I2  
i2_ml(meta_other_log)
```

```
##      I2_Total  I2_species  I2_animal  I2_key  I2_Group  I2_obs  
## 3.534049e+01 6.224198e-08 1.194546e+01 4.732340e+00 5.250613e-08 1.866269e+01
```

```
# capture.output(i2_ml(meta_other_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/I2_meta_other.csv")
```

```
meta_other_pair_log <- update(meta_other_log, ~. +pair)
```

trait pairs

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There  
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_pair_log)
```

```
##  
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 764; method: REML)  
##  
##   logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc  
## -728.9269 1457.8539 1479.8539 1530.7914 1480.2078  
##  
## Variance Components:  
##  
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R  
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000   75    no  species  no  
## sigma^2.2 0.0333 0.1825   75    no  animal  yes  
## sigma^2.3 0.0276 0.1662  100    no    key  no  
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  244    no  Group  no  
## sigma^2.5 0.0774 0.2781  764    no    obs  no  
##  
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:  
## QE(df = 758) = 875.8051, p-val = 0.0019  
##  
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:6):  
## QM(df = 5) = 8.4561, p-val = 0.1328  
##  
## Model Results:  
##
```

```

##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.1984  0.1196   1.6583  0.0973  -0.0361  0.4328
## pairgrowth-fertility -0.0244  0.2906  -0.0838  0.9332  -0.5939  0.5451
## pairgrowth-maturation -0.0408  0.1295  -0.3153  0.7526  -0.2947  0.2130
## pairgrowth-size      -0.0310  0.1032  -0.3003  0.7639  -0.2332  0.1712
## pairmaturation-fertility -0.0096  0.0823  -0.1171  0.9068  -0.1709  0.1517
## pairmaturation-size  -0.1738  0.0746  -2.3299  0.0198  -0.3201 -0.0276
##
## intrcpt              .
## pairgrowth-fertility
## pairgrowth-maturation
## pairgrowth-size
## pairmaturation-fertility
## pairmaturation-size  *
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_pair_log)
```

```

##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.0437215      0.4651611

```

```

# save(meta_other_pair_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_pair.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_pair_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other_pair.csv")
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_pair_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_other_pair.csv")

```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,-1,0,0,0))
```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairgrowth - maturation = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      808
## 2      807  1 2.0596    0.1513

```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,0,-1,0,0))
```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairgrowth - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)

```

```
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 0.2592 0.6107
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,0,0,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairmaturation - fertility = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 0.4609 0.4972
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,1,0,0,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - fertility - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 0.1646 0.685
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,1,-1,0,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - maturation - pairgrowth - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 808
## 2 807 1 3.3116 0.06879 .
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,1,0,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
```

```
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - maturation - pairmaturation - fertility = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 1.9006      0.168
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,1,0,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - maturation - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 12.628 0.0003801 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,0,1,-1,0))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - size - pairmaturation - fertility = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 0.0949      0.758
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,0,1,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairgrowth - size - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
```

```
## 2    807  1 4.6638    0.0308 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_pair, c(0,0,0,0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## pairmaturation - fertility - pairmaturation - size = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~pair
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     808
## 2     807  1 8.4329  0.003685 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
meta_other_lab_log <- update(meta_other_log, ~. +lab_field)
```

lab vs field

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_lab_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 764; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -733.8814 1467.7629 1481.7629 1514.2145 1481.9114
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000   75    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0511 0.2260   75    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0186 0.1363  100    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  244    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.0781 0.2794  764    no    obs    no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 762) = 879.4184, p-val = 0.0020
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 3.0806, p-val = 0.0792
```

```
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.3029  0.1644   1.8425  0.0654  -0.0193  0.6251 .
## lab_fieldlab     -0.2070  0.1180  -1.7552  0.0792  -0.4382  0.0242 .
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_lab_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.03355246    0.48924480
```

```
# save(meta_other_lab_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_lab.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_lab_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other_lab.csv")
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_lab_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_other_lab.csv")
```

```
meta_other_sex_log <- update(meta_other_log, ~. +sex)
```

```
sex
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_sex_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 764; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -733.4765  1466.9530  1482.9530  1520.0301  1483.1445
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0000    75    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2  0.0374  0.1935    75    no  animal  yes
## sigma^2.3  0.0231  0.1520   100    no    key  no
## sigma^2.4  0.0000  0.0000   244    no  Group  no
## sigma^2.5  0.0779  0.2791   764    no    obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 761) = 877.9654, p-val = 0.0020
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 3.0067, p-val = 0.2224
##
```

```
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt      0.1523  0.1202   1.2673  0.2051  -0.0832  0.3878
## sexfemale   -0.0130  0.0743  -0.1751  0.8610  -0.1587  0.1327
## sexmale     -0.1581  0.0996  -1.5863  0.1127  -0.3534  0.0372
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_sex_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.01708017      0.44702071
```

```
# save(meta_other_sex_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_sex.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_sex_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other_sex.csv")
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_sex_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_other_sex.csv")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_sex, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## sexfemale - sexmale = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~sex
##
##   Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1      811
## 2      810  1 3.7284    0.0535 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
meta_other_stage_log <- update(meta_other_log, ~. +stage)
```

life stage

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_stage_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 764; method: REML)
##
##      logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -730.4285  1460.8571  1478.8571  1520.5569  1479.0971
```

```

##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000   75    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0658 0.2565   75    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0071 0.0842  100    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  244    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.0788 0.2807  764    no    obs   no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 760) = 871.7128, p-val = 0.0030
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:4):
## QM(df = 3) = 9.4871, p-val = 0.0235
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.2362  0.1552   1.5223  0.1279  -0.0679   0.5404
## stageboth       -0.0544  0.1104  -0.4933  0.6218  -0.2708   0.1619
## stagecross      -0.1758  0.0691  -2.5451  0.0109  -0.3112  -0.0404 *
## stagenon_adult  -0.0443  0.0928  -0.4769  0.6334  -0.2262   0.1376
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_stage_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.03538611      0.49888592
```

```

# save(meta_other_stage_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_stage.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_stage_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other_stage.c
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_stage_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_other_stage.
linearHypothesis(meta_other_stage_log, c(0,1,-1,0))

```

```

## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stageboth - stagecross = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##      Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1         761
## 2         760  1  1.8207    0.1772

```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_stage_log, c(0,1,0,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
```

```
##
## Hypothesis:
## stageboth - stagenon_adult = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     761
## 2     760  1 0.0079     0.9291
```

```
linearHypothesis(meta_other_stage_log, c(0,0, 1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## stagecross - stagenon_adult = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~stage
##
##   Res.Df Df   Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1     761
## 2     760  1 3.0138     0.08256 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
meta_other_design_log <- update(meta_other_log, ~. +Design_rename)
```

experimental design

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
summary(meta_other_design_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 764; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -732.7163 1465.4327 1481.4327 1518.5098 1481.6242
##
## Variance Components:
##
##   estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000   75    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0293 0.1713   75    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0277 0.1665  100    no    key    no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  244    no   Group  no
```

```
## sigma^2.5 0.0770 0.2774 764 no obs no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 761) = 873.6304, p-val = 0.0028
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 3.8233, p-val = 0.1478
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.0649 0.1083 0.5997 0.5487 -0.1473 0.2771
## Design_renamegenotype 0.1276 0.1035 1.2330 0.2176 -0.0752 0.3305
## Design_renamepedigree 0.1687 0.1025 1.6453 0.0999 -0.0323 0.3697 .
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_design_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.03646206      0.44672434
```

```
# save(meta_other_design_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_design.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_design_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other_design_log.txt")
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_design_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_other_design_log.txt")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_design_log, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## Design_renamegenotype - Design_renamepedigree = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~Design_rename
##
##      Res.Df Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1         762
## 2         761  1 0.0895    0.7648
```

```
meta_other_narrow_log <- update(meta_other_log, ~. +narrow_broad)
```

narrow vs broad genetic correlation

```
## Warning in rma.mv(yi = zr_sign, V = log_vi, random = list(~1 | species, : There
## are rows/columns in the 'R' matrix for 'animal' for which there are no data.
```

```
## Warning: Rows with NAs omitted from model fitting.
```

```
summary(meta_other_narrow_log)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 763; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -733.3134 1466.6267 1482.6267 1519.6933 1482.8185
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor  R
## sigma^2.1 0.0000 0.0000   75    no  species  no
## sigma^2.2 0.0544 0.2331   75    no   animal  yes
## sigma^2.3 0.0229 0.1513   99    no     key  no
## sigma^2.4 0.0000 0.0000  243    no   Group  no
## sigma^2.5 0.0777 0.2788  763    no     obs  no
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 760) = 883.3371, p-val = 0.0012
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 0.1379, p-val = 0.9334
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.1114 0.1393  0.8003  0.4236 -0.1615  0.3844
## narrow_broaddominance  0.0147 0.2167  0.0677  0.9460 -0.4101  0.4395
## narrow_broadnarrow    0.0289 0.0781  0.3702  0.7112 -0.1241  0.1819
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
r2_ml(meta_other_narrow_log)
```

```
##      R2_marginal R2_conditional
##      0.001332823  0.499118449
```

```
# save(meta_other_narrow_log, file = "model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_narrow.RData")
# capture.output(summary(meta_other_narrow_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/meta_other_narrow")
# capture.output(r2_ml(meta_other_narrow_log), file = "model output/sensitivity_log/R2_meta_other_narrow")
linearHypothesis(meta_other_narrow_log, c(0,1,-1))
```

```
## Linear hypothesis test
##
## Hypothesis:
## narrow_broaddominance - narrow_broadnarrow = 0
##
## Model 1: restricted model
## Model 2: ~narrow_broad
##
```

```
## Res.Df Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## 1 761
## 2 760 1 0.0046 0.9461
```

```
#for other traits
#load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other.RData")
class(meta_other_log) <- "rma.mv"
I2_CI <- I2(meta_other_log, other_pair_data_log$log_vi , ME = FALSE, sims = 10000, phylo = "animal", obs
I2_CI
```

calculate I2

```
## I2_Est. 2.5% CI 97.5% CI
## species 0.0000 0.0000 0.0000
## animal 0.1192 0.0869 0.1547
## key 0.0473 0.0354 0.0604
## Group 0.0000 0.0000 0.0000
## obs 0.1867 0.1696 0.2039
## phylo 0.3365 0.2608 0.4113
## Vt.VT 0.3532 0.3242 0.3828
```

```
# write.csv(I2_CI, "model output/sensitivity_log/I2_CI_meta_other.csv")
```

8.4 SN figures

Can load saved data if don't want to run above code

```
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_pair.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_lab.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_sex.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_stage.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_survival_narrow.RData")

load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_pair.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_lab.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_sex.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_stage.RData")
load("model/sensitivity_log/meta_other_narrow.RData")
```

```
#pdf("figure_output/sensitivity_log/intercept_pair.pdf", width=12, height=8, onefile=F)
```

```
survival_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival, mod = "1", group = "key", data = survival_pair,
xlab = "Effect size (Zr)") + scale_fill_manual(values = "purple") + scale_colour_manual(value
survival_pair_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_pair, mod = "pair", group = "key", data =
```

```

      xlab = "Effect size (Zr)")

other_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other, mod = "1", group = "key", data = other_pair_data),
      xlab = "Effect size (Zr)") + scale_fill_manual(values = "orange") + scale_colour_manual(values = "orange")

other_pair_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_pair, mod = "pair", group = "key", data = other_pair_data),
      xlab = "Effect size (Zr)")

ggarrange(survival_plot, survival_pair_plot, other_plot, other_pair_plot, ncol = 2, nrow = 2,
      labels = c("A", "B", "c", "D"), common.legend = T)
#dev.off()

```

Fig SN1. intercept only and pair models

```

#pdf("figure_output/sensitivity_log/moderators_both.pdf", width=12, height=12, onefile=F)
survival_lab_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_lab, mod = "lab_field", group = "key", data = meta_survival_lab),
survival_sex_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_sex, mod = "sex", group = "key", data = meta_survival_sex),
survival_stage_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_stage, mod = "stage", group = "key", data = meta_survival_stage),
survival_design_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_design, mod = "Design_rename", group = "key", data = meta_survival_design),
survival_narrow_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_survival_narrow, mod = "narrow_broad", group = "key", data = meta_survival_narrow),
other_lab_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_lab, mod = "lab_field", group = "key", data = meta_other_lab),
other_sex_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_sex, mod = "sex", group = "key", data = meta_other_sex),
other_stage_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_stage, mod = "stage", group = "key", data = meta_other_stage),
other_design_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_design, mod = "Design_rename", group = "key", data = meta_other_design),
other_narrow_plot <- orchard_plot(mod_results(meta_other_narrow, mod = "narrow_broad", group = "key", data = meta_other_narrow),

ggarrange(survival_lab_plot, other_lab_plot,
      survival_sex_plot, other_sex_plot, survival_stage_plot, other_stage_plot, survival_design_plot, other_design_plot,
      common.legend = T)
#dev.off()

```

Fig SN2. other moderators